

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.6 Report on the dissemination and training activities no. 1.

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1. Event Reporting by date

1.1. May 2018 – April 2020

May, 2018

Kick off Meeting

Workshop (1)

Conference (1)

June, 2018

Networking Events (1)

Training Sessions (1)

Workshop (1)

Action Learning Seminar (1)

July, 2018

Workshop (1)

Summer school /Seminar (1)

Seminar (1)

September, 2018

Action Learning Seminar (2)

WP/Partners Meeting (4)

Discussion Panel/Fair (1)

Conference (2)

October, 2018

Action Learning Seminar (1)

Focus Group (1)

Conference (3)

Workshop (1)

November 2018

Focus Group (1)

Conference (2)

Workshop (1)

Training Session (1)

December, 2018

Training Session (1)

Conference (1)

Workshop (2)

January, 2019

Action Learning Seminar (1)

Focus Group (2)

February, 2019

Workshop (2)

Training Session (2)

Webinar (1)

WP/Partners Meeting (1)

March, 2019

Workshop (7)

Conference (2)

Webinar (1)

Focus Group (3)

April, 2019

Workshop (3)

Webinar (2)

Focus Group (3)

Seminar (1)

May, 2019

Workshop (1)

Public Event (1)

WP/Partners Meeting (1)

Focus Group (3)

Dissemination event (1)

1st Consortium Conference (1)

June, 2019

Conference (2)

Webinar (1)

Seminar (1)

Action learning Seminar (2)

Focus Group (3)

Workshop (1)

July, 2019

Workshop (1)

September, 2019

Training Session (1)

Workshop (1)

Public event (1)

Round Table/Fair (1)

Conference (1)

October, 2019

Public Event (1)

Conference (3)

Focus Group (1)

WP/Partners meeting (1)

November, 2019

Conference (1)

Seminar (1)

Training Session (1)

December, 2019

Public Event (1)

Webinar (1)

WP/Partners meeting (1)

Focus Group (1)

January 2020

Workshop (1)

WP/ Partners meeting (1)

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Webinar (1)

Focus Group (1)

Conference (1)

Action Learning Seminar (1)

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Workshop (2)

Focus Group (1)

Round Table (1)

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March 2020

Virtual Conference (1)

Workshop (2)

Focus Group (1)

April 2020

Workshop (1)

May, 2018

Event title	Kick off Meeting “NEXTFOOD: Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrofood system”
Place	Malmö, Sweden
Dates	May 2 – May 4, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	The 19 partners of NEXTFOOD: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (Sweden) 2. Lund University (Sweden) 3. University of Oradea (Romania) 4. University of South Bohemia (Czech Republic) 5. Norwegian University of Life Sciences (Norway) 6. American Farm School (Greece) 7. Alma Mater Studiorum- Università di Bologna (Italy) 8. Bioinstitut (Czech Republic) 9. The Forestry Research Institute of Sweden (Sweden) 10. Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia (Greece) 11. Centre International Hautes Etudes Agronomiques Mediterraneennes (France) 12. Deutsche Welthungerhilfe (Germany) 13. SEKEM Development Foundation (SDF) (Egypt) 14. Mekelle University (Ethiopia) 15. Alexander Technological Institute of Thessaloniki (International Hellenic University) 16. Iseki-Food association (Austria) 17. Roskilde University (Denmark) 18. University of Gastronomic Sciences (Italy) 19. Universidad De Chile (Chile)

The **Kick-off** meeting of the European Program Horizon entitled: “NEXTFOOD: Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrofood system” was held at Malmö (Sweden) on 2-4 May 2018.

The project concerns a new model of agricultural knowledge co-creation and its integration into university syllabi, namely action-learning. This model focusses on creating synergies between academics, farmers and professionals and using their dynamics as the engine for establishing continuously evolving platforms of knowledge, understanding and skills.

In the framework of NEXTFOOD project 10 distinct cases studies will be implemented, aiming at the integration of action learning model in agriculture.

During the kick-off meeting the 19 partners of the project discussed the challenges of the model and set some guidelines.

Event title	National student Conference "INNOVATIVA", 7th Edition
Type	Conference
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	9-12 May, 2018
Event aim & purpose	National student conference that has presenting the researches of young scientists
Relevance to the project	During the student conference, the audience present at this event was informed about the NEXTFOOD project's objectives, partners and the developments up to that moment
Type of audience	Students, professors, academic staff from University of Rzeszow, Romanian Food Sector Union, University of Suceava - Stephan the Great, University of Arad - Vasile Goldis, Technical University of Cluj Napoca
Estimated size of targeted audience	90
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
Goal of presence	Examination of new opportunities for young specialists from food science field.

Event title	Foresight4Food International Workshop
Type	Workshop / Focus Group Interview
Place	Montpellier, France
Dates	22-24 May, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Dissemination of NextFood project on an international arena. Networking for potential collaboration.
Relevance to the project	The aim to develop the global food system
Type of audience	The participants (academic, food industry, NGO) explored other initiatives that are working with skills and exchanged information for future collaboration.
Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	Networking and dissemination of results. Better connections are needed between science and processes of policy dialogue, business engagement and societal learning
	Foresight4Food is an initiative supported by a group of international organizations, food systems researchers, business players and civil society organizations. The collective aim is to enhance foresight and scenario analysis for the global food system. There is a need for improvements in how food system changes are explained and visualized.

June, 2018

Event title	Presentation of NextFOOD
Place	European Commission in Brussels
Dates	Coordinator's day
Event aim & purpose	Networking
Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Estimate size of target audience	70
Geographical scope of event	International
Goal of presence	Multi-actor Support
	NextFood was presented at coordinator's day at the European Commission in Brussels. A very good opportunity to network with other projects also focusing on learning and a multi-actor approach.

Event title	Action-Learning Model
Place	Vineyards of the Greek case. Kilkis, Greece
Type	Training Session
Dates	June 6, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Networking event
Geographical scope of event	International

Partner(s) involved	American Farm School Rutgers University (NextFood associate partner)
Estimate size of target audience	30
Goal of presence	Synergies between academics Action Learning Agriscapes – the Greek case study of NextFood. Vineyards and animal farms supported by the American Farm School consultants are hosting students and faculty of the Alexander Technological Education Institute of Thessaloniki.

Event title	Agroecology: Action Learning in Farming and Food Systems. Norwegian Case Study.
Type	Workshop
Dates	May – June 2018

Place	Norway
Type of audience	Students, researchers, experts.
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	60
Partner (s) involved	Norwegian University of Life Sciences

The video shows excerpts from a student-planned and student-led workshop held in a previous version of the course.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZkM05F9GI6w&feature=youtu.be>

Event title	Experiential and action learning in sustainable gastronomy. Italian Case Study.
Place	Pollenzo, Italy
Dates	May-June 2018
Event aim & purpose	Action Learning Seminar:

	World Food Cultures and Mobility Sustainable agriculture and agroecology
Type of audience	Students, Researchers, Academians
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences
Estimate size of target audience	25
Goal of presence	A systemic and action approach

July, 2018

Event title	Wetlands as socio-ecological systems in a changing world: from theory to practice
Type	Seminar

Place	Santiago, Chile
Dates	July 11, 2018
Event aim & purpose	To disseminate bases and results of the “Practica II” model, developed by the teachers team from the undergraduate program “Renewable Natural Resources Engineering” from the University of Chile.
Relevance to the project	A concrete example of a successful teaching model for practical work in the field that could be used as a reference for other programs related to agri-food systems.
Type of audience	Undergraduate Students from the program “Renewable Natural Resources Engineering”, Teachers and Faculty Authorities.
Estimated size of audience	50
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Chile
Goal of presence	Dissemination of NEXTFOOD within the teacher’s team to start collaboration regarding new educational methodologies.
	The “Practica II” model combines teaching, extension and research in a simultaneous way, taking as main aim the knowledge of wetlands. It was an event that presented the teachers and students perspective regarding their experience with this model.

Event title	Workshop:Identification of Collaborations
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	16 July, 2018

Event aim & purpose	NEXTFOOD was presented to students, high-school students, teachers and academic staff.
Relevance to the project	This is the kick-off meeting of the project when all the possible interested parties were invited in order to identify the partners who would like to support and get involved in the project.
Type of audience	Students, high-school students, teachers, academic staff, staff from agri-food related public institution and stakeholders from the private sector from Michael the Grate Highschool, Technological Highschool Cadea, Technological Highschool Salonta, National Consumer Protection Agency Bihor branch, Department of agriculture Bihor branch, Ruska Laszlo Individual Enterprise, Silena Ltd, Protimix Ltd.
Estimated size of targeted audience	32
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
Goal of presence	Preselection of the participants and presentation of the outlines of the implementation. More than half of the participants were enrolled in the project,
	Kick-off meeting of the project when all the possible interested parties were invited in order to identify the partners who would like to support and get involved in the project.

Event title	Fall in love with Polish food
Type	Summer school within the CEEPUS network

Place	Poland
Event aim & purpose	Summer school for students
Dates	June 28 -July 9, 2019
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from both universities.
Estimated size of target audience	30
Goal of presence	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
	Attended by the students involved in the Nextfood project. The students and staff preselected had the opportunity to open new horizons in an international environment.

September, 2018

Event title	Master Course
Type	Action Learning Seminar
Place	Norway
Dates	September 3, 2018
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partner(s) involved	Norwegian University of Life Sciences

The Master course in Agroecology at NMBU. Students get a rich experience of food production by working one full day at a farm in Norway.

The ultimate goals of the master's course are to reduce the distance between academia and society and to bridge the all too frequent gap between knowing and doing with regard to complex challenges such as sustainability of agrofood systems.

Event title	WP1 -Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Budweis, Czech Republic
Dates	September 4, 2018
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	International

Event title	TransTisza Agriculture Days
Type	Conference
Place	Debrecen, Hungary
Dates	5-6 September, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Celebration of 150 years of agrofood academic education
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from both universities and many other universities, research institutes and companies from Europe.
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
Goal of presence	Presentation of a case study in the field of Romanian case.
	Presentation made by Dr. Timar Adrian on the <i>development of an innovative product - Using</i>

of natural additives in the meat processing being closely related to the activities foreseen in the Nextfood project.

Event title	Presentation of NextFOOD project. Presentation of the Table Grapes Case Study.
Type	Discussion Panel Informing visitors of the 83 rd TIF-Helexpo about the NextFood Project aims.
Place	Thessaloniki, International Fair, Greece
Dates	September 9, 2018
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
Estimate size of target audience	100

Type of audience	Government, Research Institutions and Universities, Growers, Companies
	<p>A discussion panel was organized at the Innovation HUB of Thessaloniki International Fair premises.</p> <p>This exhibition is the biggest and most important in Greece and has a track record of almost a century.</p> <p>The panel presented the table grapes case study. Participants were selected in order to represent the triple helix according to European Commission Smart Specialization - S3 approach.</p> <p>This approach mainly focuses on bringing together all interested parties and has them discuss and co-decide upon all important issues especially those of Strategic Planning.</p>

Event title	Action Learning Agriscapes
Type	Action Learning Seminar
Place	Kilkis, Vineyards of N. Greece
Dates	September 10, 2018
Event aim & purpose	<p>A new innovative technology was demonstrated.</p> <p>Digital skills to be acquired by students of agronomy faculties and early professionals are critical for the future of successful farming consultancy.</p>
Type of audience	Farmers, specialists, MSc students
Estimate size of target audience	25

Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
	<p>The methodology applied is called photonics and it can be described as non-destructive diagnostic method that can be used in order to estimate the levels of several substances of grapes in the field.</p> <p>The measurements are geotagged and a farmer has the chance to acquire a good knowledge of the maturity status of his/her produce within minutes.</p> <p>This can be very helpful in terms of programming the harvest and negotiating the sale of the produce.</p> <p>The production of high-quality products can be the result of merging agricultural experience, scientific knowledge and incorporation of high technology in everyday farming routine.</p>

Event title	Greek case in Fokhol farm
Type	WP2/Partners Meeting
Place	Norway
Dates	September, 2018
Event aim & purpose	The Greek case is getting familiarized with the Action Learning Model in Fokhol farm.
Estimate size of target audience	35
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Norwegian University of Life Sciences American Farm School

Event title	WP1 Meeting
Type	WP/Partners Meeting
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	September 10-11, 2018
Event aim & purpose	To discuss and create a roadmap for the first year of work in wp1.
Estimate size of target audience	16
Relevance to the project	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in wp1.
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	RUC, LU, SLU, ISEKI, University of Calcutta, Universidad De Chile, CHIHEAM.
	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in wp1.

Event title	22nd Sief International Ethological Food Research Conference. Tradition and nutritional science in the modern food chain.
Type	Conference
Place	Kalamata, Greece
Dates	September 26-28, 2018
Event aim & Purpose	Dialogue with academic partners in the forms of presentations and workshop.

Relevance to the project	Interaction and dialogue with stakeholders + dissemination of the Nextfood project.
Type of audience	Academics in the food culture sector
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	80
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School Lund University
	<p>The teams of Greece & Lund University took advantage of the 22nd Sief International Ethnological Food Research Conference in Kalamata, September 2018 to organize a workshop on the coordination of their WPs.</p> <p>At the same time, the Greek team organized a raw cheese sensory evaluation event.</p> <p>Dissemination of project and opportunity to have dialogue with academic partners in the food culture sector.</p> <p>https://www.siefhome.org/wg/fr/events.shtml</p>

Event title	WP2-Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Pollenzo, Italy
Relevance to the project	Presentation of the “Diffused University Project” in Torino, Italy. One of the event’s major themes is encouraging access to learning by generating dialogue in which science and traditional knowledge are given equal dignity.
Dates	September, 2018

Estimate size of target audience	40
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, SLU, UNIOR, USB, AFS, BIOINSTITUT, SKOGFORSK, CIHEAM, WHH, SDF, MEKELLE, IHU, IFA, UNISG
	<p>Representatives of the 12 NEXTFOOD cases met in Pollenzo, Italy, for a joint development of the project action research method.</p> <p>The vision of NEXTFOOD, stakeholders in the agrifood and forestry chain working together for developing a sustainable education, was captured in this creative sketch.</p>

October, 2018

Event title	Greek case study
Type	Action Learning Seminar
Place	Elassona, Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October, 2018
Estimate size of target audience	15
Partner(s) involved	International Hellenic University
	DAY 1

Greek case study: The pilot phase

Visit to a sheep farm in Ellassona. Five-member group consisted of a breeder, a student, a professional, an academic and an observer of the process.

DAY 2

Greek case Study:

Vets, students and farmers getting familiarized with the use of infrared thermography in cattle and sheep health.

Event title	7th International Meeting of Young Food Technologists 10th Anniversary of Students Scientific Group of Food Technologists “FERMENT”
Type	Conference
Place	Rzeszow, Poland
Dates	October 19 – October 21, 2018

Event aim & purpose	Researches of young scientists, students and staff was presented.
Geographical scope of event	International
Type of audience	Students and staff of the universities
Estimated size of target audience	50
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea Dr. Timar Adrian presented the necessity of food innovation in order of providing food with higher quality for the consumers satisfaction and avoiding food wasting. The NEXTFOOD participants Students, researchers, professors from Romania had the opportunity to enhanced their skills and get familiarized with new ITC skills, in an international environment.

Event title	Focus group
Type	Focus Group
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October, 2018
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	20
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School Lund University

	<p>Focus group with advisors: Dr Hakan Jonsson from Lund University met with the Greek field agronomists and animal scientists at the premises of American Farm School. A successful focus group was conducted.</p> <p>Focus group with farmers: Table grape producers at Nea Peramos, Kavala reflected on farming issues with the support of the two moderators, Professor Hakan Jonsson from Lund University and Dr Chrysanthi Charatsari from American Farm School.</p>

Event title	"Ecotrophelia" 7th Edition
Type	National student conference
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	October 31 – November 02, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Presentation of case studies on food innovation by students coordinated by academic staff from different Romanian universities.
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from different universities from Romania.
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimated size of target audience	52
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea

	Event for best case studies related with food innovation in Romanian universities by students
Event title	International Conference of Educational Innovation in Agricultural Topics
Type	Conference
Place	Lima, Peru
Dates	October 17-19, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Disseminate and exchange knowledge on the best educational practices in agrarian topics in order to promote innovation in higher education and contribute to consolidate some of the SDGs.
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	100
Type of audience	Researchers, teachers and students and other stakeholders related to education in agrarian topics.
Partner(s) involved	University of Chile
	<p>Prof. Osvaldo Salazar from the University of Chile, presented NEXTFOOD project in the “International Conference on Innovational Education in Agrarian Topics” last October in Lima, Perú.</p> <p>This event was organized by National Agrarian University La Molina (Perú) and the North American Colleges and Teachers of Agriculture – NACTA.</p>

The purpose of the Conference was to disseminate and exchange knowledge on the best educational practices in agrarian topics in order to promote innovation in higher education and contribute to consolidate some of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This was an opportunity to make dissemination of the project with Institutions representing Latin American and North American Countries.

<http://www.lamolina.edu.pe/cieta/english/>

Event title	Skogforsk case – introductory meeting
Type	Information and workshop
Place	Uppsala, Sweden
Dates	October 26, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Meeting with the Skogforsk case-team to introduce the Nextfood model and the Skogforsk case

Relevance to the project	WP 2 case study
Type of audience	Experts who will participate in the case
Estimated size of targeted audience	5
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	To meet with our case-team
	A constructive discussion about the planned case study

November, 2018

Event title	WP1- Focus group interview about skills
Place	Alnarp, Sweden
Dates	November, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Involving stakeholders in the inventory of skills needed for future professionals.
Relevance to the project	Part of WP1
Estimated size of targeted audience	8
Geographical scope of event	National

Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	Representatives of food manufacturing industry, extension specialists, national federation of farmers, and university, examined a list of skills with high importance in the future. The Coordinator of Next Food consulted the focus group attendees.

Event title	"Ecotrophelia" 7th Edition
Type	National Student Conference
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	October 10 – November 2, 2018
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimated size of target audience	52
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
	<p>Presentation of case studies, related with food innovation in Romanian universities, by students coordinated by academic staff from different Romanian universities.</p> <p>The audience was informed about the NEXTFOOD project and the conference allowed the students to have similar activities with those foreseen in the project.</p> <p>Students, academic staff from different universities from Romania.</p>

Event title	AgriBusiness Forum 2018
Type	Business forum
Place	Serres, Greece
Dates	November 01-03, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Enhancing issues affecting the improvement of the level of cross-sectoral cooperation interconnecting research & development
Relevance to the project	Interaction and dialogue with stakeholders + dissemination of the Nextfood project.
Type of audience	Business professionals in the agrofood sector
Estimated size of targeted audience	150-200
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Lund University American Farm School
Goal of presence	Dissemination of project and opportunity to have dialogue with business practitioners. http://agribusinessforum.org/agrifood-next-is-here-serres-greece-1-3-11-2018/

Event title	Workshop in strategies for sustainable agrifood systems and natural resources in Chile and Sweden
Type	Workshop
Place	Santiago, Chile
Dates	November 22-23, 2018

Event aim & purpose	To know research areas related to Agri-food systems and Natural Resources of the workshop participants in order to promote collaboration networks between Chile and Sweden.
Type of audience	Researchers and teachers from Chilean and Swedish Universities.
Estimated size of audience	60
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Chile Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	Dissemination of NEXTFood project within Chilean and Swedish researchers Networking. Dr. Martin Melin was invited to present the NEXTFood project to other Chilean and Swedish colleagues. Possibility for collaboration on the topic of sustainable education. http://www.workshopchilesweden.uchile.cl/

Event title	Visit at Recas vineyards
Type	Training Session
Place	Recas, Romania
Dates	November 28, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Annual visit of the students to Recas vineyards where practical activities took place – sensory analysis, tasting different

	types of wines, observing the technological process.
Relevance to the project	Identification of Recas Company as a possible stakeholder in the Nextfood project
Estimated size of target audience	48
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from University of Oradea and Recas Company
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
	The students involved in the NEXTFOOD projects and interested in developing a product in the field of vines had the opportunity to observe the technological process, actively ask questions on the products and equipment. Identification of Recas vineyards as a possible stakeholder in the Nextfood project.

December, 2018

Event title	Planning part I Skogforsk case – introductory meeting
Type	Infoday/Training Session
Place	Uppsala, Sweden
Dates	December 3, 2018

Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target of audience	10
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Type of audience	Researchers met with contractors and crew in the forest
Event aim & purpose	Meeting with the team of forestry contractors to introduce the Nextfood-case and discuss the content.
Relevance to the project	<p>Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain. Using the Nextfood model to gain a higher level of understanding about logging (techniques, strategies and methods) to increase the quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity.</p> <p>A constructive discussion about the planned case study.</p>

Event title	International Conference of Young Scientists INNOVATIVA 2018
Type	International Conference
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	December 13 – December 15, 2018
Event aim & purpose	New approaches in foodstuff preparation like slow cooking, using natural extracts, fusion cuisine combining of agrifood raw materials were presented by students from Romania and Poland.
Type of audience	Students, academic staff
Estimated size of target audience	35
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea ISEKI
	<p>Among the participants there were members of the team involved in NextFOOD project. During the conference, Timar Adrian, presented the initiative of ISEKI 2019 Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition Game, from NextFOOD consortium, to young researchers from universities</p> <p>Students were interested in the competition especially students from Bsc and just one from Msc.</p>

Event title	The NextFood Project: Drawing together a vision
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Type	Workshop
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	December 14-15, 2018
Estimate size of target audience	30
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Deutsche Welthungerhilfe- University of Calcutta
	<p>The Nextfood pedagogy is tried and tested in Kolkata, India under Indo-Norway collaboration programme in education by Nextfood partner Welthungerhilfe and University of Calcutta.</p> <p>The concluding workshop with students, faculties and guests was during 14th-15th December in Kolkata.</p>

Event title	Long term climate pattern. Introduction of new varieties.
Type	Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	December 17, 2018
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	35
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
Type of audience	Academics, Agronomists, Field Consultants, table grape farmer group leaders.

A workshop was organized by SPMO bringing together academics from Aristotle University, AFS agronomists, field consultants and table grape farmer group leaders.

The long-term climate patterns in their respective locations, in Greece were analyzed and decisions regarding the introduction of new varieties and the management of existing ones were taken.

After an extremely difficult year for our farmers, climatic resilience is not just a future concern, it is an immediate challenge.

January, 2019

Event title	Action Learning in Action
Type	Master Course
Place	France
Dates	January, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	25
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Centre International Hautes Etudes Agronomiques Mediterraneennes

Event aim and purpose

CIHEAM students of the master course in Organic Agriculture brainstorming and setting the scene for engaging territorial stakeholders in the course project...3 groups working within the Park of Coastal Dunes on promoting organic cheese production, ancient crop variety recovery and a Park organic menu.

Event title	Workshop in General Assembly of ČTPEZ 2019
Type	Focus Group
Place	Czech Republic
Dates	January 17, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The event focus was on identifying the main challenges of practice abstract evaluation.
Type of audience	All sector stakeholders
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	20

Partner(s) involved	Bioinstitut University of South Bohemia
	This focus group allowed us to draft the evaluation tool under WP 5.

Event title	Workshop in General Assembly of ČTPEZ 2019
Type	Focus Group
Place	Czech Republic
Dates	January 19, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The event focus was on identifying the main competences of students with the relevance to practice
Type of audience	Practitioners
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	20
Partner(s) involved	Bioinstitut University of South Bohemia
	This focus group with farmers and advisors allowed us to draft the evaluation tool under WP 5.

February, 2019

Event title	Rumore: 3rd Workshop of the Local Stakeholders Group
	RUMORE Rural-Urban Partnerships Motivating Regional Economies is an Interreg Europe project
Type	Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February 4, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia
Event aim and purpose	Presentation of NextFood project. NextFood partners, the Agronutritional Cooperation Region Central Macedonia presented NextFood project to the Local Stakeholders Group of RUMORE.

Event title	Romanian Case
Type	Training Activity
Place	Vinnicky, Slovakia
Dates	04-08 February, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Training for Sensory analysis of sweet wines in Vinnicky
Relevance to the project	A team of students from the NEXTFOOD project - Micle Loredana, Farcut Madalin,

	Kanalus Laura, Goian Madalina and teacher Timar Adrian attended a training for Sensory analysis of sweet wines in Vinnicky, Slovakia in order to have an overview about professional foodstuff sensory analysis.
Type of audience	Students, academic staff
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimated size of target audience	5
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
	<p>Identification of opportunities and collaborations by setting up common future activities in the field of agri-food sector.</p> <p>New trends in vine production for increasing the skills and knowledge of NEXTFOD beneficiaries from the teams.</p> <p>One of the teams chose vine as topic for their innovative foodstuff.</p>

Event title	Placing, IoT Digitanimal Collars at goats
Type	Training Session
Place	Ierissos, Chalkidiki, Greece
Dates	February 15, 2019
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	15

Relevance to the project	Farmers learn how to monitor their animals grazing.

Event title	Enhancement of new cheese product with traditional features
Type	Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February 21, 2019
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	35
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia American Farm School
	Presentation of Nextfood project. The Agronutritional Cooperation RCM, the American Farm School and the Institute for

Employment and Vocational Training in the framework of NextFood project, held a workshop with main aim the development of a new cheese product with traditional features and geographic identity, in the Regional Unit of Kilikis.

Within this context, the participants explored the necessary skills that will strengthen the manufacturing, entrepreneurship and competitiveness of the sector.

Event title	SSC- Introduction to the Sustainable Supply Chain Competition in Sustainable Aquaculture
Type	Online Webinar
Dates	February, 26, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The purpose was to outline the general instructions for the teams (requirements, team composition), the evaluation criteria; outline each of the complimentary online trainings (including upcoming assignments); and intellectual property rights.

Relevance to the project	The Introductory Webinar was the first of 6 webinars given to the student teams that have enrolled into the SSC.
Type of audience	Master's students
Estimated size of target audience	11-or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association University of Bologna
	Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 4.7.
	To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 4.5.
	Participants were asked to answer what was the best part of the webinar: “!The Video Call and Smooth and flexible interaction ... and answer all questions immediately”; “when we received the explanation of the presentation of our project”; “The best part of this webinar was to know what we will do in the future webinars.”; and “Your positiveness and that you motivated us”..
	https://food-sta.eu/ssc-2019

Event title	Co-design of a future Master Program in Agroecology and Sustainable food systems
Type	Workshop
Place	Pollenzo, Italy

Dates	February 26-27, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomy Science <i>Researchers from the 12 NextFood Cases</i>
	<p>Nextfood took part in the co-design of a future Master Program in Agroecology and Sustainable food systems.</p> <p>Together with faculty staff and students from the University of Gastronomy Science and representatives from the Slowfood movement, Nextfood partners discussed the design of a one-year MSc program integrating the action-oriented and learner-centric Nextfood approach.</p> <p>The new program is an extension of the existing and well-renowned action-learning courses at the UNISG, which have been further developed as one of the cases of Nextfood.</p> <p>The delegates left Pollenzo with a positive spirit, not at least as a result of the insightful contributions made and the enthusiasm expressed by the UNISG students invited to the workshop.</p>

March, 2019

Event title	“EBAMA day”
Type	Workshop
Place	Chania, Greece
Dates	March 1, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	40
Partner(s) involved	Centre International Hautes Etudes Agronomiques Mediterraneennes
	<p>Nextfood presented at CIHEAM Chania, Greece!</p> <p>Lamberto Lamberti, officer of CIHEAM Bari, has been invited at CIHEAM Chania to present the H2020 Research & Innovation project Nextfood, highlighting and sharing his experience as team leader of the “action learning” case study carried out at the Bari institute.</p> <p>The presentation was given, during an event organised in the framework of the European Union project “Broaded Agriculture by Multifunctional Activities-EBAMA” funded by ERASMUS +.</p> <p>The focus of the event was on skills and competencies in rural development and how the development of new curricula can support them.</p> <p>The project Nextfood has been identified as an interesting opportunity for sharing experiences in consideration of its objective: promoting the transition to innovative education and learning in Sustainable Farming and Food Systems (SFFS) that relies on the combination of knowledge and action to cope with the complexity of SFFS.</p> <p>Moreover, it offered a focus on the project case study methodology based on the</p>

	adoption of “Action learning” within learning and research processes at different levels (master, undergraduate, vocational, doctoral), enhancing the co-creation of innovation and knowledge and inducing a paradigm shift from a linear to a cyclical approach of learning.

Event title	Research Day
Type	Conference / Poster presentation
Place	Pollenzo, Italy
Dates	March 13, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Presentation of the NextFOOD Project on the Research Day.
Type of audience	Academic audience: researchers, professors, students, visiting professors
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	70
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences
	<p>During the “Research Day”, organized by UNISG NextFood project was introduced to BSc, MSc and PhD students, researchers, UNISG Professors, Professors from other Universities, entrepreneurs and industry . The participants were interested in the introduced activities.</p> <p>https://www.unisg.it/eventi/2019-research-day/</p>

Unisg Research Day 2019

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TnUf_cxs0rs

Event title	Kick-off workshop Nextfood Project
Type	Workshop
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	March 13-14, 2019
Event aim & purpose	To explore the shifts needed in order to make the transition to experiential, active learning and for allowing time for individual and group reflection.
Type of audience	High-school students, teachers, students, academic staff, representatives of companies and state institutions from UNIOR, NMBU, "Mihai Viteazul" Technical HighSchool, "Emanoil. Gojdu" National College, Technological Highschool Salonta, Department for Agriculture, Consumer protection agency.
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimated size of target audience	50

Partner(s) involved	<p>University of Oradea</p> <p>Norwegian University of Life Sciences</p>
	<p>It is the first workshop organized in co-operation with NMBU in order to explore the shifts that our educational needs towards achieving active learning.</p> <p>The identification of the partners that are going to be involved in the training programme proposed by the UNIOR. The presentation of Nextfood, the active learning model, etc.</p> <p>All the persons invited at this event agreed to take part in the training programme.</p> <p>Informal meetings with a large number of stakeholders from public and private sector were also conducted in order to have an overview about the potential interested stakeholders that will be involved in the Case. Joining on research teams, internships at the students and stakeholders' requests, jobs, participating in different events related to agrofood sector - like fairs, conferences, workshops, summer or winter schools and valuable databases with relevant references.</p>

Event title	Transforming Agri-Food system
Type	Focus Group
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	March 19, 2019
Event aim & purpose	<p>There were altogether 17 participants representing various stakeholder groups.</p> <p>The courses planned for UoC as a case, are planned for: A. Extension workers/farmer trainers. B. Food entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Hence getting input from various stakeholders who are either receiver of the course or last beneficiary of the course (for example, farmers will receive further training by the extension workers trained through this course).</p> <p>The aim was to find out different skills from different sectors which will be important for the course.</p>
Relevance to the project	<p>Skills and knowledge required to be included came from the meeting were selected and included in the new curriculum. Curriculum were changed and modified as per the recommendations.</p> <p>Identified the group of students we are looking for. Development workers, government officials were convinced along with the farmer trainers to take this course.</p> <p>Communication with the conventional agriculture universities and department to include these in their courses are part of our future agenda.</p>
Type of audience	Farmer -3, Entrepreneur –3, Extension Worker -3, Professor -3, Sustainable Agriculture Trainer -2, Researcher -4,
Geographical scope of event	National

Estimate size of target audience	17
Partner(s) involved	Deutsche Welthungerhilfe- University of Calcutta
	Focused Group Discussion with farmers, activists, researchers and entrepreneurs to map required skills and competencies for transforming Agri-Food system.

Event title	Workshop in the framework of Nextfood project
Type	Workshop
Place	Sindos, Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	March 19, 2019
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	300

<p>Partner(s) involved</p>	<p>International Hellenic University American Farm School Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia</p>
	<p>NextFood project was presented at the participants, as the Next Tool for the development of an efficient education system, equipped with new training methods for the transition to more sustainable agrifood and forestry systems.</p> <p>The main aim of the co-organizers, with the participation of the students of the Animal Production Department, the Plant Production Department and the Food Technology Department, was the identification of gaps in curricula and the co-creation of new training practices.</p> <p>Special attention was given in the digital soft skills that the next generation of professionals requires. The interaction with the undergraduate students led to the assumptions that action-oriented and participatory learning are crucial for the design of new educational systems that will overcome the sustainability challenges of the 21st century.</p>

Event title	SSC- Student Presentation Webinar
Type	Webinar
Dates	March 19, 2019
Event aim & Purpose	Each team of the SSC gave a 5- to 10-minute presentation on the practical experience the members have in the competition-specific sector e.g. an internship they did, a visit to a company, volunteer activity. If no one on the team had any practical experience, they were encouraged to visit an aquaculture-related company.
Relevance to the project	This webinar is number 2 out of 6 webinars given to the student teams that have enrolled into the SSC.
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association UNIBO-University of Bologna
Geographical scope of event	International
Type of audience	Master's Students
Estimated size of target audience	5-or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device
	<p>Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is the most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 4.3</p> <p>To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 4.6.</p> <p>Participants were asked to answer what was the best part of the webinar: “getting to know all other contestants”; “Teamwork the spirit of cooperation... Diversity and richness of information”.</p> <p>https://food-sta.eu/ssc-2019</p>

Event title	Focus group discussion with farmers and experts
Type	Focus group
Place	Abiadi, Ethiopia
Dates	March 25, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Inventory of skill and knowledge gap with in farmers and development agents. Data collection.
Relevance to the project	Identify the gap and start training university students based on these gaps
Type of audience	Development agents, farmers and instructors
Estimated size of targeted audience	20 (each group with 10 participants)
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Begasheka FTC

Event title	Kick off workshop planning meeting
Type	Workshop/ Bilateral meeting
Place	Mekelle, Ethiopia
Dates	March 26, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	5
Geographical scope of event	International
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Norwegian University of Life Sciences

	<p><i>Adjustment of the template for the kick-off workshop for this case and plan practicalities and roles:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Update different workshop schedules (for participants and facilitators). -Assign specific roles to all five, in line with schedules. -Prepare sheets with questions per session. -Preview the room. -Talk through the Ethiopia case (past, present, immediate future).

Event title	Launch of the Ethiopian Case 3.
Type	Workshop (27/03) Visiting Farmers' Training Centers and St. Merry college facilities (28/03)
Place	Mekelle (27/03), Ethiopia Wukro and Sekata (28/03)
Dates	March 27-28, 2019
Type of audience	University management, university instructors, Bureau of agriculture office responsible for FTCs, NMBU staffs, MSc students of Agroecology and Sustainable Development
Estimated size of targeted audience	26
Geographical scope of event	International
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Norwegian University of Life Sciences
	Mohammed Tilahun, Girmay Tesfay and Zenebe Abraha of the Ethiopia case team, together with Tor Arvid Breland and Lutgart Lenaerts of the NMBU team, successfully

launched the Ethiopia case of the Nextfood programme on 27 March 2019 at Mekelle.

Thanks to excellent participation and contributions from all participants, important input to the Ethiopia case was generated.

The next day, they visited important 'learning arenas' for the Ethiopia case, namely a Farmers Training Center (FTC) and an Agricultural Technical and Vocational Education Training College (ATVET).

In the next cycle of the Ethiopia case, these learning arenas will serve as entry points to farmers and other important stakeholders for the students of Mekelle University's Master's programme in Agroecology.

Event title	WP2 -Reflecting and planning the Agroecology Course in Kerala
Type	Workshop

Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	March 27, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The purpose was to plan the curriculum for 'Short Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education', a case under the Nextfood project by initiating a dialogue among stakeholders.
Relevance to the project	The workshop succeeded in creating a shift in mind-set, process and content with regard to the educational activities at University of Kerala to suit the Nextfood objectives.
Type of audience	Students, mentors, researchers, teachers, policy makers.
Estimated size of targeted audience	15
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	WHH-University of Kerala Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences Norwegian University of Life Sciences
	The workshop, conducted in IGP model succeeded in identifying the tools for practicing the shift from lecture hall to a diversity of learning arenas; from lecturing to co and peer learning and from textbook to a diversity of teaching aids/a variety of learning sources by conducting Short Course on Agroecology.

Event title	International Symposium on Agroecology and Public
Type	Conference (March 29) Focus Group (March 28)
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	March 28-29, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Popularizing the theme 'agroecology' and 'Short Course on Agroecology and Action Learning' in Kerala and dissemination of research output of Centre for Agroecology and Public Health
Relevance to the project	Materializing Nextfood objectives necessities creation of platforms where stakeholders can interact and co create knowledge and so, the initiative is significant.
Type of audience	University Authorities, Researchers, Professors, Social Activists, Journalists, Bureaucrats, Representatives from farmer groups, LSG and agribusiness sector.
Estimated size of targeted audience	120
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	WHH-University of Kerala Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences Norwegian University of Life Sciences
On March 28 , Nextfood Coordinator Martin Melin (SLU) conducted a focus group interview with the Director of Internal Quality Assurance Cell, University of Kerala, Gabriel Simon Thattil and Former Registrar, University of Kerala, Jayaprakas, M., as well as the Kerala case leader Manju S. Nair, Kerala case teachers Megha Radhakrishnan and Anupama Augustine, all University of Kerala, and NMBU Nextfood team members	On March 29 , 2019, the Dep. of Economics, University of Kerala (UoK) organized an International Symposium of Agroecology, where they had the official inauguration of Centre for Agroecology and Public Health (CAPH), and launched the Certificate Course on Agroecology; Action Research and Education, which is one of the Nextfood cases. The symposium acted as a platform to meet likeminded people and the dissemination of research output of

Geir Lieblein and Anna Marie Nicolaysen (photographer on this occasion).

international collaboration (with Nextfood project).

April, 2019

Event title	SSC- In the Field
Type	Webinar
Dates	April, 4, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of the “In the Field” Webinar was that one or more companies will present a case study in which they would explain a process- or product-related problem and how they solved it.

Relevance to the project	This webinar is number 3 out of 6 webinars given to the student teams that have enrolled into the SSC.
Type of audience	Master's students
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association UNIBO-University of Bologna
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimated size of target audience	8-or more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device
	<p>Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is the most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 4,75.</p> <p>To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 3,75.</p> <p>Participants were asked to answer what was the best part of the webinar:" the presentation about quality assessments and certification"; "I just could see the last two presentations because the audio and video of the other presentations were not working."</p>

Event title	Working Lunch Event
Type	Workshop/Bilateral meetings
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	April 5, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	100
Geographical scope of event	National

Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia
	<p>The Vice-President of the Government and Economy and Development Minister, along with General Secretaries of the Economy and Development and Agriculture Ministries were the official guests.</p> <p>During the constructive conversation the President of ACRCM Mr. Konstantinos Kiltidis raised the concern for the future of the Agri-food Sector in four key areas: markets, productivity, profitability and next professionals, in the framework of NextFood project.</p>

Event title	Focus Group – WP1 Inventory of Skills
Type	Focus group
Place	Pollenzo, Italy
Dates	April 5, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences
	<p>Meeting with nine stakeholders from 7 enterprises was organized It was facilitated by Prof. Paola Migliorini and her two assistants: Dr. Natalia Rastorgueva and MS Nicholas Panayi.</p>

	<p>The meeting started with brief presentation of the NEXT FOOD project and current activities if UNISG.</p> <p>Participated stakeholders represented different enterprises (different activities), therefore the skills needed for future agri-food system professionals are as wide as the food system itself. From the conversations that arose during this workshop, it became clear that the food companies and entrepreneurs of today are involved in a wide variety of activities which the future agri-food system professional needs to have an understanding of.</p> <p>From a sustainability perspective, future professionals need to have an understanding and adaptability to the environmental challenges as well as familiarity with energy and waste cycles. They need to be open to innovations and to embrace synergies between different sectors and cultures.</p>

Event title	European Agriculture the Next Day
Type	Workshop/Multi-Conference
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	April 12-14, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	50
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia
	The sectors that the convention highlighted were the following: tourism and culture, agriculture and agrofood, technologies,

	<p>energy and the environment, infrastructure, financing tools for businesses.</p> <p>The main focus was on the need for new policies to be designed for the development of agriculture, livestock, forestry and fishery and presented the European project Nextfood, which investigates the policies that must be exercised on” Educating the next professionals in the agrofood sector “.</p> <p>Nextfood project aims to deliver policy recommendations that will impact the future education and training systems, for the maintenance of the existing and the creation of new job positions, throughout the agrofood and forestry production chain.</p> <p>Towards this direction the participants raised their concern over the adaptation of the regional and national policies that will foster the adoption of sustainable agriculture practices.</p>

Event title	Presentation of NextFOOD project. Workshop.
Type	Presentation meeting
Place	Bologna, Italy
Dates	April 16, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the meeting is to present NEXTFOOD project to UNIBO colleagues involved in coordination of degree programmes and educational innovation with the aim to set possible collaboration and synergies.

Relevance to the project	The meeting had the aim to find possible collaborations with people involved in coordination of degree programmes in veterinary and agrofood sciences at UNIBO or involved in educational innovation in order to have suggestions and feedback particularly useful for the assessment and recommendation on educational policies in the agri-food systems at regional and national level. It also aims at aligning the project and innovative teaching approaches promoted at UNIBO.
Type of audience	<p>Programme coordinators of bachelor degree programmes in: Aquaculture and Fish Production Hygiene, Animal Production, Marketing and Economics of the Agro-industrial System, Agricultural Technology, Food Technology, Ornamental plants and landscape protection.</p> <p>Programme coordinators of master of science degree programmes in: Animal Production Science and Technologies, Food Science and Technology, Safety and Quality in Animal Production, Agricultural Sciences and Technologies, Veterinary Medicine</p>
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	12
Partner (s) involved	University of Bologna
	<p>Organization of the meeting to present the aims of the NEXTFOOD project and its new proposed educational approach and to set possible collaboration between the project and the degree courses in the agri-food sector actually present at UNIBO.</p> <p>A debate on the possible innovation tools for the current education at UNIBO, and how coordinators of degree programmes at UNIBO could give a contribution to the project. Also understanding of importance of international research projects in supporting local innovation initiatives in education.</p>

Event title	SSC- Student Suggestion Webinar
Type	Webinar
Dates	April, 16, 2019
Event aim & purpose	This webinar was number 4 out of 6 webinars as part of the SSC Competition on Sustainable Aquaculture. The student teams were asked to submit beforehand 3 suggestions for topics to be presented and discussed by experts.
Geographical scope of event	International
Type of audience	Master's students
Estimated size of target audience	9-or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device
	<p>Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is the most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 3,6.</p> <p>To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 3,6.</p> <p>https://food-sta.eu/ssc-2019</p>

Event title	SCAR SWG AKIS 4 - 11th Meeting
Type	Seminar
Place	Dublin, Ireland
Dates	April 15-17, 2019

Event aim & purpose	Learning and feedback from interactive project approaches.
Relevance to the project	Exchange of best practices with other multistakeholder projects. Improving interactive approach in Nextfood.
Estimated size of audience	30
Type of audience	Academics, project managers, extension specialists.
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner (s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	To share best practices and learn from other projects. To disseminate the Nextfood project to an audience interested in multi-stakeholder initiatives.

Event title	Focus group discussion with farmers and experts
Type	Focus group
Place	Senkata, Ethiopia
Dates	April 23, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Inventory of skill and knowledge gap with in farmers and development agents. Data collection.
Relevance to the project	Identify the gap and start training university students based on these gaps
Type of audience	Development agents, farmers and instructors

Estimated size of targeted audience	20 (each group with 10 participants)
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Melfa FTC

Event title	Focus Group: Identifying skills for sustainable food production
Type	Focus Group
Place	Santiago, Chile
Dates	April 29, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Identify skills and gaps present in professionals related to sustainable food production.
Relevance to the project	Important step to develop WP1 task 1.1: inventory of skills.
Type of audience	Stakeholders related to sustainable food production: farmers, teachers/researchers, students and agronomists.
Estimated size of targeted audience	13
Geographical scope of event	Regional
Partner(s) involved	UCH
Goal of presence	Gather different stakeholders of agri-food systems in the Chilean context. Identify skills and gaps in the professionals of agri-food systems in Chilean context.
	Skills mentioned by the participants: observation capacity, system thinking, knowledge of your environment (ecological, social, economic), continuous learning capacity.
	They mentioned other skills related to agronomists and advisors, besides the skills mentioned above, they mentioned communication skills, work with other disciplines, association and

	cooperation capacity (networking), ethics and empathy.

May, 2019

Event title	Greek NextFood Case
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	May 9, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partners Involved	AFS, NMBU, IHU

Event title	Slow Fish / A Biennale Event organized by Slow Food in Genoa
Type	4-days fish Festival/Public event
Place	Genoa, Italy
Dates	May 12, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Promotion of sustainable fishing and aquaculture.
Relevance to the project	An international event is a good audience to introduce the NEXTFOOD project to the stakeholders and potential users.
Type of audience	Relevant students, future students and different stakeholders of agri-food systems from different parts of Italy and different countries.
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	50
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences NEXTFOOD project was presented by Prof. Paola Migliorini during the SLOW FISH, a biennial event organized by SLOW FOOD in Genoa, for the promotion of sustainable fishing and aquaculture. The project approach and project activities were of a great interest among youth. Current Bachelor and Master students of UNISG participated in further discussion of the project and asked the practical application of the project facilities. The feedback was positive from relevant and future students, as well as from people involved in educational activities.

<https://slowfish.slowfood.it/en/useful-info>
<https://www.unisg.it/slow-fish/edizione-2019/>

Event title	CIHEAM Bari's Action Learning experience
Type	Workshop
Place	Casa del Mare
Dates	May 13, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	20
Partner(s) involved	Centre International Hautes Etudes Agronomiques Mediterraneennes Final workshop concluding the first cycle of CIHEAM Bari's Action Learning experience in the framework of Nextfood project.

	Students of the Organic Agriculture Master course, joined by the CIHEAM Bari team, present their findings to the stakeholders of the Parco delle Dune Costiere for contributing to the sustainable development of the local agro-food system.
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Event title	WP1 Focus Group
Type	Nextfood Focus group
Place	Odense, Denmark
Dates	May 14, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Involving stakeholders in the inventory of skills needed for future professionals.
Type of audience	Farmers
Estimate size of target audience	7
Relevance to the project	To ensure that the research represents the perspectives of relevant practitioners and stakeholders

Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	RUC
	RUC conducted the focus group interview. A successful focus group with new perspectives and network.

Event title	WP1 Focus Group
Type	Nextfood Focus group
Place	Odense, Denmark
Dates	May 14, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Involving stakeholders in the inventory of skills needed for future professionals.
Type of audience	Fishermen and stakeholders within the fishing industry Farmers
Estimate size of target audience	6
Relevance to the project	To ensure that the research represents the perspectives of relevant practitioners and stakeholders
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	RUC
	RUC conducted the focus group interview. A successful focus group with new perspectives and network.

Event title	WP1 Focus Group Discussion on Inventory of Skills
Type	Focus Group Discussion
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	May 16, 2019
Event aim & purpose	To understand the skills needed by stakeholders for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio value chains in the context of Kerala
Type of audience	Farmers, Researchers, Teachers, Students
Estimated size of audience	12
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala
	<p>Centre for Agroecology and Public Health hosted the FGD and moderated the FGD.</p> <p>Nextfood aims to create foresight-based inventory of skills relevant for all regions and insights from FGD (transcript and thematic report of the FGD) can contribute towards the same.</p> <p>The FGD is a platform which interacts with different stakeholders and support the understanding of skills needed for agroecological transition.</p>

Event title	Presentation of NextFood project
Type	Dissemination Event
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	May 22, 2019
Estimate size of target audience	120
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region Central Macedonia
	<p>The attendees were members of the agrofood sector – associations, producer groups, universities, institutions, regional chambers of commerce, politicians and corporate affiliates- that share a common vision for innovative farming and processing in Greece.</p> <p>The discussion was centered on the implementation of NextFood project which will enhance educational methods and production practices.</p> <p>It was emphasized that the co-creation of knowledge and the synergies between all stakeholders are crucial for sustainable agrifood and forestry systems.</p>

<https://youtu.be/tdQ6vopbLFM>

Event title	1st CONSORTIUM CONFERENCE
Place	Budweis, Czech Republic
Dates	May 27-29, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	50
	<p>On May 28 – 29, NextFOOD held its first annual consortium conference in Budweis in Czech Republic. The conference combined short presentations by each work package with experiential learning in workshops.</p> <p>The rationale for planning the event in such a way is our attempt to build a community of practice through active participation of every consortium member, where we together achieve a higher understanding of the project's purpose and goals.</p> <p>In the initial catching-up session, participants shared their experiences from the past year's work and engaged in discussions about part-time achievements as well as concerns for the future. After a series of short presentations, we were up-to-date with the status in each work package and achieved an improved view of the whole of the project.</p> <p>The richness of the data collected from case studies, focus groups and surveys is already impressive and will help us in our aim to produce high quality research. In the workshops that followed, the participants gave feedback and shared their ideas on different tasks and pressing issues, and thereby contributed to the collective knowledge of the project.</p> <p>The two days ended by a session where we reflected on what we had achieved and not achieved in relation to the intended outcomes of the conference, and used that as the starting point for looking towards the near future of the project.</p>

	<p>The meeting in Budweis demonstrated the great potential of this consortium. But there is still a long and winding road ahead to make Nextfood an established, reputable, and sustainable learning community that can contribute to the transition of higher education and professional training in the agrifood and forestry sector, and influence national and European research and education policies.</p> <p>To obtain this, we need commitment to the original ideas of NextFOOD – an education system for sustainability based on experiential and student-centered learning, as well as endurance and high-quality work from all partners.</p>
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June, 2019

Event title	22th European Seminar on Extension and Education
Type	Conference

Place	Acireale, Sicily
Dates	June, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	200
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School Lund University
	<p>A research paper conducted within the framework of NEXTFOOD project. More than 200 scientists from all over the world, professors, specialists and experts in the field of agricultural extension participated in this seminar which took place in Acireale, Sicily.</p> <p>The paper focuses on the multiple meanings of sustainability in agricultural knowledge and information systems and was conducted by Dr.Chrysanthi Charatsari, Dr. Håkan Jönsson and Dr. Philip Papadopoulos.</p>

Event title	METRIK Seminar
Type	Seminar
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	June 6, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Seminar for the research group 'Metrik, RUC' with the purpose of inspiration and collaboration.
Type of audience	Researchers/teachers at Roskilde University

Estimate size of target audience	20
Relevance to the project	To ensure that the research represents the perspectives of relevant practitioners and stakeholders
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	RUC
	The focus was to disseminate the project and get feedback from relevant academics.

Event title	“Identify skills and lack of skills in sustainable aquaculture”
Type	Focus group
Place	Ozzano dell’Emilia (BO), Italy
Dates	June 7, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the Focus group is to get information, exchange ideas and discuss about the skills currently necessary and those lacking in the field of sustainable aquaculture production chain in a future perspective.
Relevance to the project	The Focus group is contributing to WP1 task by collecting, from the point of view of stakeholders, researchers and students, information about the skills important in the context of sustainable aquaculture, the concept of sustainability in the aquaculture production chain, and how research and education in this sector can help to fill gaps in student skills and competencies,

	particularly relevant in the daily practice in the aquaculture field.
Type of audience	4 stakeholders (2 fish farmers, 1 aquaculture consultant, 1 veterinarian), 1 researcher from a public diagnostic lab, 2 academic teachers working in the field of aquaculture and fish pathology, 2 students of the degree in Aquaculture and Hygiene of Fish Productions and Safety and Quality of Animal Productions.
Partner(s) involved	University of Bologna
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	12 (9 participants + moderator and co-moderator)
	<p>Organization and moderation of an informal and restricted discussion group as WP4 Leader in order of the collection of data useful for WP1 tasks on sustainable aquaculture in view of UNIBO long-lasting expertise in this field.</p> <p>The discussion was focused in the list of skills important in the aquaculture production chain.</p> <p>A debate on sustainability of the aquaculture sector and on the role of research and education in this context.</p> <p>Involvement of stakeholders for discussing and cooperating on new learning practical methods for a better education of the future young aquaculture professionals.</p>

Event title	“Identify skills and lack of skills around sustainable agriculture”
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Type	Focus group
Place	Kalochoi & Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	June 7 & June 13, 2019
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region Central Macedonia
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	20 (total number of both groups)
Relevance to the project	<p>The Focus group is contributing to WP1 task on “Inventory of the skills</p> <p>The 1st Focus Group was conducted at the Hellenic Agriculture Organization “Demeter”, Institute of Plant Breeding and Genetic Resources, with the participation of a group of researchers.</p> <p>The 2nd Focus Group was conducted at Kalochoi. The site was chosen because it was near the experimental station of “Demeter”. Thus, it was more convenient to find the rice growers, in the middle of rice cultivation season, in order to conduct the focus group with people from the primary production, and in this case with rice growers.</p> <p>In each case the discussion was focused on the <i>efficiency</i> in the use of <i>resources</i> (technical/economic and natural resources) and the promotion of <i>energy efficiency</i> through infrastructures to provide high-quality goods to the average consumer.</p>

Event title	High Tech Farming Platform FRESH FRUIT, Pilot Project 1st Technical Meeting in Thessaloniki
Type	Workshop

Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	June 12-14, 2019
Event aim & Purpose	Presentation of Nextfood project at demonstration farm in Kilkis. Connecting Demonstration Farms and Technology Providers.
Estimate size of target audience	60
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	<p>American Farm School Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia</p> <p>Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia, Tuscany Region and Central Macedonia Region are in close collaboration in the context of “High Tech Farming” S3 Agri-Food Platform.</p> <p>The Fresh Fruit Project of American Farm School is part of the partnership with the Region of Central Macedonia through the Smart Specialization Platform. The Fresh Fruit project is supported by the lead partner of the HighTech Farming partnership the Region of Tuscany.</p> <p>During the technical meeting there was a demonstration of a farm in the Regional Unit of Kilkis where the Greek case of Nextfood project is developing with practical implications of technologies from American Farm School and a joint session with the European Entrepreneurship Region 2018, Central Macedonia Region.</p>

Event title	ISEKI-Food Final Virtual Workshop in Sustainable Aquaculture. Case Study 4.
Type	Webinar (the last of the online trainings as part of case#4)
Dates	June 19, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	11 – or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device.
Type of audience	Student team (master's students), stakeholders (students, academia and professionals from the field of aquaculture).
Partner(s) involved	<p>ISEKI-Food Association UNIBO- University of Bologna</p> <p>At the Final Virtual Workshop all student teams presented their projects in the presence of the public and the winning team was announced.</p> <p>Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 5. To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 4.</p> <p>Participants were asked to answer what was the best part of the webinar:” The range of presenters, the relevant and open theme, providing a variety of solutions for a wider interest.”. Students engagement, motivation and practical applications of projects was of great interest. They suggested that: “More questions and discussion - students should ask questions from other teams too. This would help to develop analysis and critical thinking. Presentations could be shorter and more time for QA”; “Brief student presenters to support them to polish presentations and familiarise themselves with use of webinar technology, timekeeping, simplify presentations and organisers interventions.”;</p> <p>https://food-sta.eu/ssc-2019</p>

Event title	Fall in love with Polish food
Type	Summer school within the CEEPUS network
Place	Poland
Event aim & purpose	Summer school for students/Action Learning
Dates	17-29 June, 2019
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from both universities.
Estimated size of target audience	30
Goal of presence	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
	<p>Summer school for students.</p> <p>Attended by the students involved in the Nextfood project. Their participation in the summer school opened new horizons in different cuisine aspects and foodstuff from other regions.</p> <p>The students and the academic staff from both universities had the opportunity to open new horizons in an international environment.</p>

Event title	“Education through food: Models and practices between universities and communities”
Type	Conference
Place	Pollenzo, Bra, Italy
Dates	June 20-21, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Presentation of different education approaches
Type of audience	Academic staff
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	43
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences
	<p>The Nextfood education approach was introduced to academic staff involved in similar activities. The new master program of UNIGS, in line with Nextfood project, was presented and receive positive feedback from the audience.</p> <p>https://www.unisg.it/assets/education-and-food-20.06.2019-program-unisg-pollenzo.pdf</p>

Event title	First cycle action learning visit at FTC
Type	Action Learning Seminar
Place	Senkata, Ethiopia
Dates	June 21-22, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Train students based on Nextfood approach.
Relevance to the project	Generate evidence on the impact of the Nextfood approach for educating the next generation of professionals in the agri-food system.
Type of audience	Students, farmers, development agents and instructors
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University
	Data Collection

July, 2019

Event title	Workshop on 'Promoting Green Culture'
Type	Workshop
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	July 4-5, 2019

Event aim & purpose	The workshop was arranged to recognize and popularize the initiatives towards creating a green culture in Kerala that forms the base for agro ecological transition.
Relevance to the project	Next food project aims at promoting green culture in countries by targeting the relevant stakeholders and by improving their skills and competencies, and hence, identifying and promoting such initiatives in Kerala is significant.
Type of audience	Farmers, Farmer leaders, social activists, researchers, bureaucrats, professors, Government officials.
Estimated size of targeted audience	110
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	WHH-University of Kerala Centre for Agroecology and Public Health hosted the program by inviting eminent personalities/ organizations/ initiatives that have contributed towards promoting green culture in Kerala. Interaction with Padma Shri. Lakshmikutty Amma, the traditional healer, revealed the depth of traditional knowledge and importance of going back to the roots. Also, interactions with farmer co-operative leaders and NGOs and award-winning farmers enriched the awareness levels– Students.

September, 2019

Event title	Six electronic traps were placed in selected areas in Greece by the American Farm School
Type	Training Session
Place	Selected areas of Greece
Dates	September, 2019
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimated size of target audience	20
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
	<p>Six electronic traps were placed in selected areas in Greece by the American Farm School. They are used for the monitoring of several insect pests' populations, such as the olive fruit fly, the peach twig borer, the Oriental fruit moth, the summer fruit tortrix and the European grapevine moth.</p> <p>The iMETOS iSCOUT® insect trapping devices, of the company Pessl Instrument, periodically take a photograph of the trap's sticky surface and automatically upload the photos on the platform FieldClimate, allowing for the observation and monitoring without the physical presence of the user in the field.</p>

Event title	The Nextfood approach in the Swedish case
Type	Workshop

Place	Uppsala, Sweden
Dates	September 16, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the workshop was to achieve a shared understanding of the shift that we are aiming for and what it would require to make the shift. One of the outcomes is a plan of implementation – what, who, when and where.
Relevance to the project	To illustrate the application of the Nextfood learning-model in a case where the participants are researchers and forestry professionals
Type of audience	7 Participants. Experts who will participate in the case study and NMBU-team
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk NMBU
	Support and discussion with the NMBU-team. A constructive discussion about the learning model and application in the forestry case

Event title	Cheese 2019
Type	Cheese Festival /Public Event
Place	Bra, Italy
Dates	September 20, 2019
Type of audience	Cheese-producers from different countries, relevant and potential students, Italian food-producers
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	150
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences <p>The new NEXTFOOD approach and the new master program was introduced to stakeholders involved in cheese production.</p> <p>The public dialogue with Cheese-producers from different countries, relevant and potential students, Italian food-producers, demonstrated their interest to the new education curricula.</p> <p>https://cheese.slowfood.it/en/</p> <p>https://www.unisg.it/cheese/edizione-2019/gli-eventi-unisg/</p>

Event title	Presentation of NextFood project Workshop: Sustainable agriculture and Rural transformation of the Regional Unit of Serres
Type	Research Workshop/Round Table
Place	Trade Fair SEREXPO 2019, Serres, Greece
Dates	September 25-29, 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30 (75.000 visitors at the Fair)
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, AFS, IHU Main Objectives: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Educating and informing the inhabitants of the areas where they exist proven geothermal fields, for the potential of geothermal energy (research, drilling, transmission networks, equipment selection, holding environmental issues etc.) is considered compulsory. 2. The digitalization of production processes for the maximization of profits and the reduction of the environmental footprint in the overall value chain. 3. Analysis and adoption of new business models under the new research methods and findings. Review of existing skills and forecasting new skills through pilots and case studies as those of NextFood project. 4. Strategies in the promotion of agrofood products. 5. Enhancement of Serres Gastronomic Identity, by utilizing the local natural and cultural potentialities. <p><i>Presentation of NextFood project through dissemination activities</i></p>

<https://youtu.be/YQxYZq2mRrU>

Event title	The European Agroecology Forum
Type	International Forum/Conference
Place	Heraklion, Crete, Greece
Dates	September 26-28, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Fostering interactions between actors in science, practice and social movements, by facilitating knowledge sharing and action. The aims is the creation of an inclusive European community of professionals, practitioners and citizens engaged in agroecology.
Relevance to the project	An appropriate auditory strongly relevant to the project activities.
Type of audience	Academic staff, agroecology practitioners, youth, young researchers, representatives of local governments.
Geographical scope of event	International

Estimate size of target audience	198
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences Norwegian University of Life Sciences
	<p>Public talk, introducing the NEXTFOOD project to the agroecologists from different countries, introducing the new Master program within the frame Nextfood.</p> <p>High interest to the Nextfood approach and the the new Master program,</p>

October, 2019

Event title	Aquaculture Europe 2019
Type	European Conference
Place	Berlin, Germany

Dates	October 07-09, 2019
Event aim & purpose	In the context of the annual conference of the European Aquaculture Society (EAS), in the session of Aquaponics, it was presented by the winner students team leader Luigi Petrocchi Jasinski the project that won the Sustainable Supply Chain Competition organized by ISEKI-Food Association and UNIBO under WP2 entitled "TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE AWARENESS: IMPLEMENTATION OF AN AQUAPONIC CODE OF PRACTICE".
Relevance to the project	The Student Competition was one of the Case studies under the WP2 and it was organized by ISEKI-Food Association in collaboration with UNIBO in the context of the sustainable aquaculture.
Type of audience	Academic researchers, research institutes and stakeholders.
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	100
Partner (s) involved	University of Bologna Iseki-Food Association
	Some researchers from the audience suggested to the presenter to consider in their project also the other fish species of interest for the Aquaponics in addition to marine species. Nextfood project was presented to the participants through dissemination activities.

Event title	(Re)assessing impact: A workshop about interventions, experiments and entanglements.
Type	Conference
Place	Linköping & Stjärnholm, Sweden
Dates	October 09-11,2019
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the Conference was rethinking and reassessing the relationships which are implied and enacted by terms like “intervention”, “impact”, “experiment”, and “engagement” among others.
Relevance to the project	The aim of this Conference is relevant to <i>D5.2. Framework proposal within WP5 Quality assured knowledge transfer</i> . Theoretical and practical insights gained during the Conference contributed to developing the NextFood’s Sustainability Impact Framework.
Type of audience	The Conference involved leading thinkers and scholars from STS (Science and Technology Studies), Sociology, Anthropology, Feminist Techno-science, and Design.
Estimated size of audience	21
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Lund University
Goal of presence	Ivanche Dimitrievski participated as a reader/commentator in the Conference. The goal of his participation was to gather theoretical and practical insights as to current academic work concerning the topic of “impact”. A summary of the Conference will be available here: https://liu.se/en/research/values

Event title	Colloquium of research and development in organic farming in the Czech Republic
Type	Focus Group
Place	Czech Republic
Dates	October 15, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Meeting of organic research stakeholders in order to share their recent scientific finding in the context of sustainable agriculture
Type of audience	Scientists
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	50
Partner(s) involved	Bioinstitut University of South Bohemia
	Networking, knowledge co-creation, discussion, proposal of scientific project broker event, feedback on action learning model.
	https://www.ctpez.cz/cz/akce/prezentace-z-kolokvia-ekologickeho-zemedelstvi

Event title	Transforming Agri-Food system
Type	Agroecology Festival
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	October 19, 2019
Estimated size of target audience	50

Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Deutsche Welthungerhilfe- University of Calcutta
	<p>The Nextfood case course, organized by University of Calcutta/Welthungerhilfe, ends today.</p> <p>The last day of NextFood case course, students organized an agroecology festival in the university to share what they have learnt during the course. This was also a test of their dialogue and communication skill as change agent.</p> <p>Students demonstrated innovative models of waste recycle, board games on understanding gender role in farm and food systems and many more.</p>

Event title	WP2 - Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Event title	Vienna, Austria
Dates	October 23-25, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	International
	<p>WP2: Action Research in 12 (+1) cases During the workshop the partners had the chance to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Increase Knowledge of all of the Nextfood cases b) Had a deeper understanding of what it means to be a learning facilitator

- c) Become aware of what it means to be an action researcher
- d) Increase understanding of the potentials of a Nextfood toolbox
- e) Exchange ideas as to how the cases can learn from each other and cooperate with other work-packages in the project.

Workshop in Vienna, Austria

<https://youtu.be/Ai3DtrGvAIU>

Event title	Transforming Higher Education
Type	Conference
Place	Naanjing, China
Dates	October 28-29, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Sharing best practices of transforming higher education towards an education for sustainability
Type of audience	Faculty and students

Estimated size of audience	150
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner (s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	Several other initiatives related to Nextfood aims was presented aiming to collaboration across projects. Presentation of Nextfood and networking.

November, 2019

Event title	Public Consultation for drawing up the new strategic plan of CAP 2021-2027
Type	Conference
Place	Veroia, Greece
Dates	November 11, 2019
Event aim & purpose	ACRCM participated in the public consultation of the National Rural Network, in the framework of European Rural Development Policy, for the period 2021-2027.
Type of audience	Official guests: -Deputy Minister of Agriculture, -Vice-Governor of Agriculture Economy of the Region Central Macedonia -Vice-Governor of the Regional Unit of Imathia. -Director-General of the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development of the European Commission -Representatives from the Ministry of Agriculture

Estimated size of audience	300
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia
Goal of presence	<p>In the workshop it was highlighted the new priorities and changes concerning the proposals of the European Commission's Regulations on the Common Agricultural Policy after 2020.</p> <p>A constructive debate had been developed or the preparation of the CAP Strategic Plan 2021-2027.</p> <p>Greece is significantly behind EU average in number of farmers with basic or full agricultural education. ACRCM provided policy recommendations through the official questionnaire of the workshop regarding the education and life-long learning programs for sustainable agrofood systems.</p>

Event title	Presentation of NextFOOD project
Type	Seminar
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	November 26, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Demonstration of the benefits of an action-oriented system of learning.
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School
Estimate size of target audience	50

Goal of presence	Interaction with the students
	<p>AFS visited the University of Macedonia in Thessaloniki, Greece in order to present NextFood project to its students.</p> <p>The invitation was addressed by the Assistant Professor of the Department of Business & Management Dr. Vassiliki Grougiou and through the presentation of the program it was attempted among other issues, to demonstrate the benefits of an action oriented system of learning which is encouraged by the program in regard to the entrepreneurial reality in the agri-food sector.</p>

Event title	Second cycle action learning visit at FTC
Type	Training Session
Place	Mekelle, Ethiopia
Dates	November 29-30, 2019
Type of audience	Students, farmers, development agents and instructors
Estimated size of audience	15
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Norwegian University of Life Sciences Arato FTC
	<p>Inventory of skill and knowledge gap with in farmers and development agents.</p> <p>Identify the gap and use for training university students based on these gaps</p>

December, 2019

Event title	Agroecology Day at Uoc
Type	Fair/Exhibition
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	December 1, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The students of the three months certificate course in organized an Agroecology day. They set up different models and posters and made an exhibition of different organic products in their respective counters. Students invited different stakeholders and students and teachers of the University. The students wanted to showcase their learning from the course.
Partner(s) involved	WHH - University of Calcutta Mrs. Sudeshna Dutta, Mrs. Malabi Kanungo, Ms. Priyanka Bhadra, Mr. Partha Saha, Mr. Partha Dey, Mr. Malay Kanti Dey, Ms. Titiksha Pandit, Mr. Firoz Khan, Mr. Pramod Singh Negi
Type of audience	University Teachers, Students, Office staffs, Different stakeholders –farmers, farmer entrepreneur, researchers, NGO workers etc.
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target of audience	100
Relevance to the project	The Agroecology day is the final demonstration by the students about their learning in the course and it is also part of their evaluation process. The agroecology day also involves communication by the students so it also shows how they have improved through the course.

Event title	FoodFactory-4-Us Virtual Visit
Type	Webinar
Dates	December 3, 2019
Event aim & purpose	At this webinar, BOKU gave a presentation on Ohmic Heating of Gluten-Free Bread; Institut Français des Boissons, de la Brasserie et de la Malterie (IFBM) France gave a presentation on beer fermentation and the webinar ended with a Structured Reflection Session.
Relevance to the project	Number 3 out of 6 webinars
Type of audience	Master students
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimated size of target audience	19 attendees – or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device.
	ISEKI-Food Association organised the webinar on GoToWebinar https://food-sta.eu/ssc2019-b

Event title	Interview of academic leaders and faculty members
Type	Focus group interview
Place	Stockholm, Sweden
Dates	December 04, 2019

Event aim & purpose	To identify institutional factors that can contribute or hinder generating effective faculty collaboration for transdisciplinary and action-oriented education. The interview was built on 5 themes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Structure and organization of the higher education 2) Political and financial interests 3) Leadership of higher education 4) Democratic processes 5) Societies norms and values
Relevance to the project	The Focus group interview is part of the process in WP 2 – Case studies. The findings will contribute to the understanding of institutional factors contributing or hindering the shift to a transdisciplinary and action-oriented education in forestry and agriculture.
Type of audience	The committee of young professionals in the green sector
Estimated size of targeted audience	6
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Stakeholders engaged	The Royal Academy of Agriculture and Forestry in Sweden

Event title	WP1 Meeting
Type	WP/Partners Meeting
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	December 9-10, 2019

Event aim & purpose	To discuss and create a roadmap for the second year of work in wp1.
Estimate size of target audience	16
Relevance to the project	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in wp1.
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	RUC, LU, SLU, ISEKI, University of Calcutta, Universidad De Chile, CHIHEAM.
	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in wp1.
	Initial results of WP1 task 1.1 “Inventory of skills” were presented and discussed. It was also discussed how we best achieve awareness of the articles, reports, practice abstracts, etc., made in the project. We discussed some ideas of articles to publish. We established collaboration with WP3 to develop some tasks, specifically task 1.2.

January, 2020

Event title	Coordination of research in food systems
Type	Workshop
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	January 13, 2019

Event aim & purpose	To coordinate and share inspiration between researchers working with food systems.
Estimate size of target audience	6
Relevance to the project	To coordinate and share inspiration between researchers working with food systems.
Type of audience	Researchers and one municipal employee
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
	Inspiration, network and feedback.

Event title	WP6 – Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	January 14-15, 2020
Estimated size of targeted audience	12
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	AFS, ACRCM, ISEKI, SLU, BIOINSTITUTE
	Package's progress, challenges and suggestions for improvement.
	The NextFood dissemination team, after having completed a very productive meeting at Thessaloniki, Greece, updated the project communication plan. Tasks and duties have been reallocated and new deadlines have been scheduled.

Event title	FoodFactory-4-Us Student Suggestion Webinar
Type	Webinar
Dates	January 17, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Students were asked to submit 3 suggestions of topics. The following topics were presented: “Improving Gluten-free Bread by Novel Arabinoxylan Networks”, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, “Experimental Design”, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, “By and Co -products Value Addition in the Cereal Chain with Focus on Nutrients and Bioactives inclusive of Novel Processing”, Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences and “The Nutri Grains Cereals and Richness of Traditional Foods with it”, Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences
Relevance to the project	Number 4 out of 6 webinars as part of the FoodFactory-4-Us competition.
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	15 attendees – or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device.
Type of audience	Master’s students
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
	Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-10 the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 8. To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 8. Participants were asked to answer what was the best part of the webinar: “Gluten free bread and design of experiment”; “I like the new knowledge of grains, their processing, and their nutrition. But I really like the presentation of DOE, which is really enriching.”; “The approach to ancient grains from different aspects: technologies, nutrition, processing, research.”;

	<p>“Multiple approach to the Subject of Cereals.”; “The holistic approach provided by all the presenters.”</p> <p>To the question what could have been done better, attendees responded: “Presentations from the teachers”; “It would be better if every presenter has power point to help us visualize what they are talking about.” More Time for the webinar and More active participation of the PARTICIPANTS !!”; “The timing of the presentations, some of them were too long.”</p> <p>https://food-sta.eu/ssc2019-b</p>
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Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting with harvesting team
Type	Action Learning Seminar
Place	A harvesting site outside the city of Lycksele, Sweden
Dates	20/01/20
Event aim & purpose	Meeting with a new harvesting team participating in the case study
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – application forestry professionals
Type of audience	5 Participants. Forest machine operators who will participate.
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	To meet with our “students”

Feedback from the audience	A constructive discussion about the case study
Stakeholders engaged	Forest company

Event title	FGD
Type	Focus Group
Place	Mekelle, Ethiopia
Dates	January 24, 2020
Type of audience	Farmers, experts and instructors
Estimated size of targeted audience	21 (10-11 for each FGD)
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University Melfa FTC
	Inventory of skill and knowledge gap with in farmers and development agents. Identify the gap and use for training university students based on these gaps

Event title	“Master in Agroecology and Food Sovereignty”
Type	Master Course based on NextFood project
Place	Pollenzo, Bra, Italy
Dates	Announcement of the Open Admission in January, 24, 2020. The Master starts on September, 2020.
Geographical scope of event	International

Estimate size of target audience	40
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomic Sciences
	<p>The program of the Master was developed as part of the "NEXTFOOD" H2020 project "Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system" and result of 1 and half year of research.</p> <p>A one-year Master program is co-designed with a participatory approach of professors, researchers, students, farmers and food producers, Slow Food & Terra Madre community.</p> <p>The Master is based on Action and Experiential Learning Approach in the following key-dimensions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food Sovereignty • Sustainable Agroecosystems • Sustainable Food Systems

Event title	WP's Leaders Meeting
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Brussels, Belgium
Dates	January 29, 2020
Estimated size of audience	12
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	RUC, NMBU, UNIBO, USB, LU, AFS, SLU
	<p>Presentation of the progress and preliminary results of the NextFOOD project.</p> <p>At the meeting the project officer from the Research Executive Agency and a policy officer</p>

	<p>from DG Agri were present. Together with two expert reviewers gave valuable feedback on the deliverables and the accomplishments of tasks. Fruitful discussions followed containing ideas on what can be improved.</p> <p>Overall, the project is right on track and the European Commission is satisfied over the achievements so far.</p>

Event title	Public Consultation for drawing up the new strategic plan of CAP 2021-2027
Type	Conference
Place	Brussels, Belgium
Dates	January 29, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Speakers from the European Commission and CHAFEA presented the Annual Work Programme 2020 as well as the calls for information provision and promotion measures concerning agricultural products. The Info Day also featured a de-briefing on the initiatives of the European Commission.
Type of audience	Multi-stakeholders from institutions of EU countries. Beneficiaries of promotion funding shared their experiences with setting up and implementing promotion programmes.
Estimated size of audience	300
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region of Central Macedonia
Goal of presence	The participants had the opportunity to listen to presentations by external experts and

	<p>applicants on the challenging aspects of proposal preparation, such as market analysis and demonstrating the impact of projects.</p> <p>The event included a match-making session aiming to bring together potential partners. NextFOOD was presented to multi-actors in view of accomplishing joint actions with other projects</p>
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February, 2020

Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting
Type	Educational meeting/ workshop
Place	A harvesting site outside the city of Lycksele, Sweden
Dates	February 04, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Educational meeting and workshop - <i>Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity (Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain).</i> Introduction of the Nextfood case study followed by a workshop on sustainable forestry.
Type of audience	5 Forest machine operators
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk

	Education and action research
	<p>WP 2 Case study – forestry professionals. We will adapt the model to fit our learners and the environment in which they work. The meetings take place at logging sites where we together look at the site – before, during and after harvesting activities and have reflective dialogues on methods and results in relation to the goal to create high value micro habitats in the forest.</p>

Event title	Enhancement of PDO, PGI, TSG Food Product
Type	1st Technical Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February 5, 2020
Event aim & purpose	<p>The focus was on the enhancement of food products with specifications for the usage of PDO, PGI or TSG indications.</p> <p>Identification of the food products and the procedures for the registration applications.</p>
Relevance to the project	In accordance with the objectives of NextFOOD project the farmers should be encouraged to switch to forms of integrated rural development through the diversification of rural production.
Type of audience	Vice-Governor of the Metropolitan Area of Thessaloniki of the Region Central Macedonia RCM. Vice-Governor of Agricultural Economy of the RCM. 6 Vice-Governors of the Regional Units of the RCM.

	9 Presidents of the Chambers of Commerce of the Metropolitan Area of Thessaloniki and the Regional Units. President and Project Team of ACRCM. Journalists/Press. Professors of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.
Estimated size of audience	25
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM
	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, shared their expertise in relation to the project “FoodOmicsGR National Research Infrastructure Comprehensive Characterization of Foods” which aims to characterize food products as PDO, PGI and TSG and support R&D in the AgroFood Sector.

Event title	NextFood-Workshop in digital skills
Type	Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February, 20, 2020
Event aim and purpose	<p>During the workshop students of IHU had the chance to familiarize themselves with digital technologies</p> <p>Dr Giovanni Agati from Florence Institute of Applied Physics presented the application of photonic technologies in assessing the quality and degree of grape ripening.</p> <p>From the American Farm School Dr. Ilias Kalfas presented the development of the LoRa -</p>

	IoT telecommunications network in Northern Greece while Dr. Evdokia Krystallidou presented digital monitoring of free grazing animals.
Relevance to the project	During the creation of an inventory of skills needed in the transition towards more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains WP1 has summarized skills in eight general themes, of which one was digital skills.
Type of audience	Students and professors from the Department of Agriculture – IHU
Estimated size of audience	70
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	American Farm School International Hellenic University
	Familiarise students with digital technologies in agriculture. Students were enthusiastic. They requested similar activities soon https://www.nextfood-project.eu/nextfood-workshop-in-international-hellenic-university-ihu/

Event title	Introducing Blockchain in multi-actors of the agri-food sector Building intelligent and sustainable supply chains
Type	Workshop

Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February 22-23-24, 2020
Event aim & purpose	ACRCM and AFS hosted two workshops at the 29th Detrop Expo Boutique.
Relevance to the project	In line with the objectives of the NextFOOD project, blockchain technology was introduced to multi-actors in the agri-food sector, as well as the future of intelligent and sustainable supply chains. Agronutritional Cooperation of the Region Central Macedonia will safely create and store digital copies of business management training certificates related to the agri-food sector. The American Farm School presented the future of Greek agri-food businesses in terms of sustainability and alignment with international tech developments. Technologies used to continuously monitor and record the parameters needed to ensure the quality and traceability of products during production, processing and distribution of agri-food products.
Type of audience	The attendees were members of the agrifood sector – associations, producer groups, universities, institutions, regional chambers of commerce, politicians and corporate affiliates- that share a common vision for innovative farming and processing in Greece.
Estimated size of audience	70
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, AFS
	NextFOOD was presented through dissemination material to workshop participants and to thousands of visitors at the 29th Detrop Expo Boutique, 22-24/02/20.

Event title	FGD on Institutional Factors
Type	Focus Group
Place	Mekelle, Ethiopia
Dates	February 28, 2020
Type of audience	Instructors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	National
Partners Involved	Mekelle University
	Inventory of skill and knowledge gap with in farmers and development agents. Identify the gap and use for training university students based on these gaps

March, 2020

Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting
Type	Educational meeting/ workshop
Place	A harvesting site outside the city of Lycksele, Sweden
Dates	March 04, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Educational meeting and workshop - Increased quality and number of micro-

	habitats for enhanced biodiversity (Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain).
	WP 2 Case study – forestry professionals We will adapt the model to fit our learners and the environment in which they work. The meetings take place at logging sites where we together look at the site – before, during and after harvesting activities and have reflective dialogues on methods and results in relation to the goal to create high value micro habitats in the forest.
Type of audience	6 Participants. Forestry officials
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
	Education and action research

Event title	FoodFactory-4-Us Final Virtual Conference in Sustainable Cereals. Case Study 4.
Type	Virtual conference
Relevance to the project	Case #4 is the FoodFactory-4-Us international student competition based on participatory education and action-learning.
Dates	March 6, 2020
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Geographical scope of event	International

Estimated size of target audience	There was a total of 61 attendees at the Final Virtual Conference from both academia (faculty and students), as well as from the cereal sector (industry and associations).
Event aim & purpose	Presentation of student team' projects at the Final Virtual Conference. The Final Conference marks the end of the competition where student teams from universities worldwide have been competing in a game based on participatory education and action learning to find the best solutions to how ancient/alternative grains can contribute to improved sustainability in the cereal chain. Their projects were presented at the Final Virtual Conference.
	Overall, the ratings were very positive. On a scale from 1-10 on the usefulness of the conference, attendees rated on average 7.8. And to the question what was the best part of the conference, remarks were also positive and included remarks such as "some of the comments included " New ideas"; "the team presentations"; "That it was open to everyone and that attendees could ask questions"; "To see all these young, creative minds presenting their results." "Presentations of the student teams and answering questions"; "The different projects presented in the competition." https://food-sta.eu/ssc2019-b/timeline-and-important-dates

Event title	Sustainable transition in Food Systems
Type	Workshop
Place	Roskilde, Denmark

Dates	March 10, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Introducing theory and practices on sustainable transition in the agrofood sector.
Estimate size of target audience	15
Relevance to the project	To coordinate and share inspiration between researchers working with food systems.
Type of audience	Researchers and one municipal employee
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University Grantoftegaard, Ballerup municipality
	Facilitating theoretical and applied perspectives on transition to sustainable food systems. To create strong engagement and reflections among students of master course.

Event title	Consultation on the agroecology course at the University of Calcutta
Type	Focus Group
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	March 12, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event aim was to have a consultation process on getting their input on the skill, competencies to be covered in the course and further fine-tuning of the curriculum. The courses planned for UoC as a case, are planned for A. Extension Workers/Farmer Trainers B. Food Entrepreneurs. Hence

	getting input from various resource persons who are facilitator in the case was the main purpose of the meeting.
Relevance to the project	Skills and knowledge required to be included as proposed by the resource persons were selected and would be included in the new curriculum. Curriculum would be changed and modified as per the recommendations. The field and classroom sessions would be modified to accommodate more students from the target groups – farmer leaders, development workers etc.
Type of audience	Extension Worker - 8 Professor/Teacher - 1 Researcher - 2
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	There were altogether 11 participants representing various facilitators who were the resource persons in the 2019 course. Prof. Parthiba Basu , Mr. Anshuman Das, Dr. Ritam Bhattacharya, Ms. Sanchari Mukhopadhyay, Dr, Sanjib Dey, Mr. Saurav Ghosh, Mr. Ardhendu Sekhar Chatterjee, Ms. Shweta Bannerjee, Ms. Malini Mukherjee, Ms. Sudeshna Dutta, Ms. Anchita Ghatak
Partner(s) involved	Deutsche Welthungerhilfe- University of Calcutta A Post doctorate fellow attended this meeting and needed those skills to be identified and selected to be included and modifications required to make the course suitable for the target groups.

April, 2020

Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting
Type	Educational meeting/ workshop
Place	A harvesting site outside the city of Lycksele , Sweden
Dates	April 20, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Educational meeting and workshop - Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity (Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain).
	WP 2 Case study – forestry professionals. We will adapt the model to fit our learners and the environment in which they work. The meetings take place at logging sites where we together look at the site – before, during and after harvesting activities and have reflective dialogues on methods and results in relation to the goal to create high value micro habitats in the forest.
Type of audience	6 Participants. Forest machine operators
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Stakeholders engaged	Forest company

NextFood Partners at the Kick Off Meeting

2. Index of Tables and Graphs

2.1 Data Sheet

MAY 2018 - APRIL 2020						
TYPE	Number of Events	Number of Participants (approximately)	International	National	1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of Conferences/NextFOOD	0	0	0	0	0	
Consortium conferences	2	100	2	0	2	
WP's Partners Meetings	11	252	11	0	11	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/networking event/conference	77	2456	28	47	21	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference	20	1958	13	6	6	
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event	11	833	8	3	0	
TOTAL	121	5599	62	56	40	
	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved
Organization of Conferences/NextFOOD						
TOTAL (2018-2020)	0	0	0	0		
SUBTOTAL	0	0	0	0		0
	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved
Consortium's Conferences						
	1	50	1		02-04/05/18	1
TOTAL 2018	1	50	1	0		1
	1	50	1		27-29/05/19	1
TOTAL 2019	1	50	1	0		1
SUBTOTAL	2	100	2	0		2
	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved
WP's Partners Meetings						
	1	30	1		04/09/18	1
	1	35	1		00/09/18	1
	1	40	1		00/09/18	1
	1	16	1		10-11/09/18	1
TOTAL 2018	4	121	4	0		4

	1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	120	1		28-29/3/2019	1
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	12	1		04/04/19	1
		1	50	1		12-14/03/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	13	1		16/04/19	1
		1	12		1	16/04/19	
		1	12		1	16/05/19	
		1	20		1	23/04/19	
		1	13		1	29/04/19	
		1	20	1		13/05/19	
		1	7		1	14/05/19	
		1	6		1	14/05/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	120	1		22/05/19	1
		1	12		1	16/05/19	
		1	12		1	07/06/19	
		1	10		1	07/06/19	
		1	20		1	09/06/19	
		1	60	1		11-13/06/19	
		1	10		1	13/06/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	15	1		19/06/19	1
		1	43	1		20-21/06/19	
			20	1		21-22/06/19	
		1	20		1	00/09/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	7	1		16/9/2019	1
		2	100	1		25-29/09/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	50		1	15/10/2019	1
		1	50		1	19/10/19	
		1	70		1	26/11/19	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	15		1	29-30/11/2019	1
		1	100		1	01/12/19	
		1	15	1		03/12/19	
		1	6	1		04/12/19	
	TOTAL 2019	47	1610	20	25		17
		1	6		1	13/01/20	
		1	20	1		17/01/20	
			5		1	20/01/20	
		1	21		1	24/01/20	
		1	40	1		24/01/20	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	70		1	20/02/20	1
		1	5		1	04/02/20	
		1	25		1	05/02/20	
	1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	70	1		22-24/02/20	1
		1	10		1	28/02/20	
		1	6		1	04/03/20	
		1	61	1		06/03/20	
		1	15		1	10/03/20	

